

Phase Memory and Collective Oscillations in the Coherent Domains of Water

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Abstract

This work examines the possibility that the low-frequency vibrations observed in water through laser interferometer are expressions of the collective dynamics occurring within quantum coherent domains.

According to the Coherent Quantum Electrodynamics (CQED) framework developed by Preparata and Del Giudice, water molecules can oscillate in phase with a trapped electromagnetic field, forming coherent regions capable of storing and transmitting phase information. The observed signals may therefore represent slow modulations of these coherent oscillations, revealing a physical mechanism for phase memory and long-term organization in liquid water.

1. Theoretical Background

The theory of coherence domains, also known as Coherent Quantum Electrodynamics (CQED), originated in Italian academia, particularly at the University of Milan, around 1988. It describes how water and other condensed systems, under appropriate conditions, can organize into large domains where molecules oscillate in phase and at the same frequency (coherence domains), behaving as a single system.

This idea was first presented in 1988 in Physical Review Letters in the article titled "*Water as a free dipole laser*". According to Preparata and Del Giudice, water molecules can self-organize into coherence domains that act as "resonant cavities," capable of storing electromagnetic energy and spontaneously entering a coherent state, oscillating in phase with the resonant electromagnetic field.

These domains can capture and maintain coherent oscillations at very high frequencies. Collective coherence reduces dissipation; energy does not disperse as in a disordered system. It is as if the domain were a natural resonator, selecting and preserving only certain stable frequencies.

The typical size of a coherence domain is about ~ 100 nm. In a water sample, coherent regions and non-coherent regions (bulk water) can coexist.

An important part of the theory also suggests that coherence domains can "store" phase configurations, encoding information in the electromagnetic field confined within them. Standing waves are established inside the domains, trapped and self-sustained, which could explain why water retains traces of previous conditions.

2. Low-Frequency Modulations and Collective Dynamics

The frequencies detected with the interferometer do not correspond to the intrinsic ones of the coherence domains, given their size (~ 100 nm), as we will demonstrate later—they oscillate at frequencies 15 orders of magnitude higher.

It is more likely that what we observe are slow low-frequency modulations produced by the collective dynamics of millions of molecules.

Inside coherence domains, as we will see later, oscillations occur in the ultraviolet range (100 nm), but when coherence domains interact with each other, beatings and slow modulations (Hz–kHz) can emerge.

These modulations can manifest as phase oscillations between neighboring domains, fluctuations of the confined EM amplitude, collective reorganizations induced by external fields (terrestrial, lunar, electromagnetic fields, etc.).

In summary, coherence domains can be considered both as electromagnetic resonant cavities and as collective oscillators, whose slow dynamics manifest in the low-frequency vibrations we measure experimentally.

3. From Electromagnetic Fields to Mechanical Vibrations

What we measure with the laser interferometer are not electromagnetic signals but mechanical vibrations, let us see how the two phenomena are related.

We have seen that in coherence domains, molecules oscillate in phase with a trapped electromagnetic field.

These oscillations also mechanically involve water molecules (rotations, vibrations, collective displacements).

When coherence domains oscillate, the confined electromagnetic energy can modulate intermolecular forces; these modulations translate into micro-displacements of molecules, thus into collective mechanical vibrations.

The vibrations we measure do not come from direct molecular transitions but from collective modulations, which can be beat frequencies: the interaction of multiple faster coherent modes that “sum” into a slow frequency, or collective phase variations: domains that remain coherent but whose relative phase changes slowly.

These variations become a “code,” the information we are seeking.

By analogy, in radio transmission, an audio signal (20–15000 Hz) modulates a 100 MHz carrier wave. The carrier corresponds to the trapped electromagnetic field within a coherence domain, while the audio signal represents the low-frequency modulation. Upon demodulation, the electromagnetic signal is transformed into a mechanical vibration (sound) by a loudspeaker.

During tests, we noticed that the detected signals change depending on environmental factors (Schumann resonances, geomagnetism, applied electromagnetic fields, prayer), suggesting that the external field interacts with the domains. The domains, in turn, transform this interaction into a collective mechanical response.

The recorded mechanical vibrations could therefore be the macroscopic and slow manifestation of an internal process in which electromagnetic fields trapped in coherence domains modulate molecular movements. In other words, we are not directly measuring the electromagnetic field but its mechanical “imprint” on matter.

If the system is perturbed by an external field, the collective phase can shift and remain in that new state. In practice, the domain preserves an “oscillation pattern” that can survive even after the stimulus has ceased.

4 Summary

The experimental results obtained find a plausible interpretation within the theory of coherence domains proposed by Preparata and Del Giudice, also known as Coherent Quantum Electrodynamics (CQED).

In light of this theoretical framework, it is possible to hypothesize a link between the phase memory of coherence domains and the very low-frequency signals observed experimentally.

What is measured could correspond to slow modulations of the phase oscillations of coherence domains.

Such modulations would be able to generate oscillations in the frequency range detected (1–100 Hz), constituting a possible signature of the intrinsic phase memory of coherence domains.

In this perspective, water would appear as a physical system capable of storing and re-emitting information related to the original stimulus, later manifesting it in the form of mechanical vibrations detectable by the laser interferometer.

5. Estimation of the Coherence Domain Dimension

The idea that water coherence domains have dimensions on the order of 100 nm comes directly from the works of Giuliano Preparata and Emilio Del Giudice in the 1990s. See Arani, Bono, Del Giudice & Preparata (1995). QED coherence and the thermodynamics of water. *IJMPB* 9, 1813–1841.

This is not an experimentally measured value but a theoretical result derived from CQED models.

When an electromagnetic field, a photon, interacts with the molecule, it can provide enough energy to make an electron “jump” from one energy level to another; this process is called an electronic transition. For water, the fundamental electronic transition occurs at an energy of about 12 electronvolts (eV).

The electron can then return to the previous level by emitting a photon with energy corresponding to the jump.

The energy of a photon is related to its wavelength λ by Planck’s formula:

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$$

Substituting: $E = 12 \times 1.602 \times 10^{-19} = 1.922 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J}$

$$\lambda = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^8}{1.922 \times 10^{-18}} \approx 1.04 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m} = 104 \text{ nm}$$

This energy corresponds to electromagnetic radiation with a wavelength of about 104 nm, thus in the ultraviolet range. The wavelength of the electromagnetic radiation determines the size of the domain.

According to the theory of coherence domains (QED), such radiation can remain confined and resonant within a set of water molecules, inducing collective "in-phase" oscillations (coherent state).

To understand the confinement mechanism, consider the behavior of the electromagnetic field inside a water volume with a side of 104 nm.

For this purpose, we use Maxwell's equations, which describe the propagation of electric and magnetic fields. To define the formation of a coherence domain, it is necessary to introduce the quantum constraint, according to which the field and molecules interact reciprocally, giving rise to a self-sustained cavity.

We then write Maxwell's equations considering quantum confinement in a cube of water with a side of 104 nm:

$$\nabla \cdot E = 0$$

$$\nabla \cdot H = 0$$

$$\nabla \times E = -\mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}$$

$$\nabla \times H = \varepsilon \frac{\partial E}{\partial t}$$

Combining Maxwell's equations, the result is a partial differential equation, we obtain the wave equation:

$$\nabla^2 E - \mu\varepsilon \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

For a cubic cavity of side L , a standing-wave solution is:

$$E(x, y, z, t) = E_0 \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{L}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{L}\right) \cos(\omega t)$$

Substituting into the wave equation yields the resonance frequency:

$$f = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2L\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}}$$

Given:

$$\mu = 4\pi \times \frac{10^{-7} \text{ H}}{m} \quad \varepsilon = 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \times 1.33^2 \approx 1.565 \times 10^{-11} \text{ F/m}$$

we obtain:

$$f \approx 1.9 \times 10^{15} \text{ Hz} \quad \lambda \approx \frac{c}{nf} \approx 120 \text{ nm}$$

This value is consistent with the ultraviolet resonance corresponding to a coherence domain of ~ 100 nm.

The electromagnetic field remains trapped in quantum confinement because water molecules form a coherence domain, oscillating in phase with the field.

There are no reflective walls; confinement occurs through constructive interference and quantum coherence.

6. Quantum Coherence and Vacuum Fluctuations

In quantum mechanics, a system can be in a superposition of states; for example, a particle can be "here" and "there" simultaneously.

Coherence is the property that allows these superpositions to interfere predictably.

When a system is coherent, its state components maintain a well-defined relative phase.

When coherence is lost (a process called decoherence), the system behaves as if it were in a classical state.

Quantum coherence underlies phenomena such as lasers, superconductivity, entanglement, and quantum computing.

In biology and chemistry, it is hypothesized to play a role in cellular processes, photosynthesis, and water memory.

Quantum vacuum is not an absolute void but a state of minimal energy, characterized by continuous fluctuations due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle:

$$\Delta E \Delta t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

where $\hbar = h/2\pi$ is the reduced Planck constant

$$\Delta E \geq \frac{\hbar}{2\Delta t}$$

This implies that even in the vacuum (i.e., in the lowest possible energy state), energy cannot be exactly zero for a finite time interval.

Therefore, the electromagnetic field (and all quantum fields) continuously fluctuates; pairs of virtual particles are created and annihilated in very short times.

These vacuum fluctuations have real and measurable effects.

7. Conclusions

The coherent quantum electrodynamics model provides a plausible framework linking the microscopic coherence of water molecules to macroscopic mechanical vibrations detectable by the interferometer.

The observed low-frequency oscillations (1–100 Hz) may represent slow modulations of phase among interacting coherence domains manifestations of the phase memory intrinsic to coherent water structures.

8. Simulation

The following images are the result of a computer numerical simulation based on the theories discussed. The purpose of the simulation was to verify and visualize theoretical predictions, providing concrete support for the formulated hypotheses.

The first shows the electric field in a plane at the center of the 104 nm water cube. The intensity of the electric field is represented by the color map, where yellow represents maximum intensity and blue the minimum. At the edges, the field is zero.

Campo elettrico nel piano XY ($z = L/2$) con confinamento quantistico

The next image shows the simulation of the interaction of three coherence domains oscillating with wavelengths of 120, 125, and 130 nm. The superposition of the three confined modes generates a composite waveform whose amplitude is slowly modulated: the very-low-frequency beats (0–100 Hz) are the signature of collective dynamics and the slow phase drift between domains

We apply the FFT to the resulting signal using the following parameters (these are the ones we use in the laser interferometer): Nyquist = 100 Hz, $f_s = 200$ Hz $N = 719$ samples.

Here is the result:

Below, the photo of the laser interferometer output related to a sample of spring water from the locality of Labante (Italy).

References:

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